

Model Fitness of Effective Advertisements Using Brand Identity among Gen Z (As Part of Research Thesis)

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Abstract

Advertisements are effective in measuring / showcasing Gen Z Characteristics and the chosen brands exhibit brand identity elements at 70 Percent to be called '**Generational Advertising**'. David Aaker Brand Identity Model is shown to represent brand identity elements by Facet Model of Generational Advertising Effectiveness at 73 Percent coefficient effectively for Gen Z at coefficient 83 Percent. Gen Z can perceive brand identity elements and understand cognitive aspects of the brand advertisements effectively. For the generational cohort, who believe in social cause and 'truth' about themselves, they expect their brands to be truthful and are motivated to identify brands that differentiates in the market. Advertisers may utilize Gen Z characteristics for recognition and recall brand identity elements that suits their demands.

KeyWords: Brand Identity, Facet Model, Advertisements, David Aaker, Gen Z, Effectiveness

Introduction

1.1 Gen Z Characteristics

Generation Z is known as '**Generational Cohort**', Gen Z born between 1996 and 2009 is the first generation to grow with technology. They are known as digital natives. They have access to internet, portable digital tools and social media. This study is about developing brand identity of various categories of brands to be identified by Gen Z as consumer segment through advertisements as medium. Gen Z Characteristics identified for the study from various reports are **Communaholic, Dialoguer, Passionate, Realistic, Singularity, Self-Expressive, Digital Native and Multiple Realities**.¹

1.2 Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness

Advertising is a form of communicating a message to a consumer about a product. Its effectiveness is determined by its success in following the traditional steps are in a communication model. Advertising **effects** are ways consumers respond to an advertising message. They are grouped into five categories viz., **Perceive, Understand** or a Cognitive Response, **Feelings** or an emotional or affective response, **Associations** that set up connections in the consumers mind, **Belief**, the result of persuasion (**Wells, Moriarty and Burnett, 1991**) that advertisers can utilize as factors of **Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness** whilst targeting Gen Z as audience and potential market base.²

1.3 David Aaker Brand Identity Model

A **brand** is defined as a "name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competition". **Brand Management** is defined as 'strategic and tactical efforts to uphold and strengthen tangible and intangible aspects of

brands'. Brand identity is a strategic brand concept, a system with distinct features and attributes, reflecting as unique identifiers through external expression like advertisements determine its position and shapes brand identity as to how customers perceive brands (**American Marketing Association (AMA)**).³

The concept of **brand identity** is an idea of what a brand is, what it should be and what it aspires to be. Identity is a planned, selection of identifiers, components and elements, brand positioning and a strategic brand definition. Brand identity is enhanced with presence of unique brand features to stand out among others, complex, resource-intensive non-copying possibility, necessity to be first and best, controllable key product attributes and brand attributes demanded by consumers.

1.4 Need for the Study

Gen Z as an evolving generation expresses unique demands that separate them as generational cohort in the economy. Gen Z's individualistic self-expression and sense of togetherness as a community create gap in the market for products and services. Their dialogue via social media shows advertisements as a medium create, rebrand identities and as such there is demand to measure advertising effectiveness as a communication medium.

1.5 Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the impact on Gen Z on advertising medium based on brand identity (David Aaker Brand Identity Model).
2. To critically evaluate the characteristics of Gen Z as consumers of advertising and its effectiveness (Facet Model).

1.6 Research Gap

Changing dimensions of 'Gen Z' as a generational cohort creates demand for gender fluidity, product placements and brand preferences.

Advertisements as a marketing medium shall follow techniques to reach Gen Z as a demanding segment with unique characteristics. Advertisers and brand experts need to impact them by integrating those dimensions that resemble as a persona, beliefs, perception, understanding, feelings, emotions and as connectors to the online world with various aspects of their life.

1.7 Research Methodology

Source of Data: Primary & Secondary Data

Secondary Study: Books on Advertising, historical and current data from Reports and Surveys on Gen Z, Articles from online and offline sources.

Sample Population: Gen Z in the age group of 17-27 (more than 100000)

Sample Size: 400 decided using Cochran Formula. Cochran's sample size formula for categorical data at alpha level a priori for .05 (error of 5%) is $n_0 = (t)^2 * (p)(q) / (d)^2 = 384$. n_0 is the sample size, t is the value for alpha level (1.96) in each 25 tail at 95% confidence level, d is margin of error, p is estimated proportion of the population, $q = 1 - p$, $p * q$ is variance.

Sample Design: Convenience Sampling. Samples were drawn from different colleges (students) and

1.10 Demographic Profile Of Gen Z

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of Gen Z

Demographic Profile of Gen Z		Frequency	Percent
Age	17-21	264	66
	22-27	136	34
Gender	Male	205	51.2
	Female	195	48.8
Educational Qualification	Pursuing Graduation	212	53
	Pursuing Post Graduation	37	9.2
	Graduate	86	21.5
	Post Graduate	44	11
	Diploma Holder	21	5.2
Occupation	IT Sector	50	12.5
	Government	27	6.8
	Industry	12	3
	Service Sector	42	10.5
	Business & Other Industries	11	2.8
	Unemployed & Student	258	64.5

Table 1.1 explains demographic profile of the sample of the study. While **Age Group (17-21)** show **264** in frequency at **66 Percent**, **Age Group (22-27)** is **136** in frequency at **34 Percent**. **Gender** of Gen Z, **Male** show frequency of **205** at **51.2 Percent** and **Female** has frequency of **195** at **48.8 Percent**.

Towards **Educational Qualification**, Gen Z **Pursuing Graduation** show frequency of **212** at **53 Percent**, **Pursuing Post Graduation** has frequency of **37** at **9.2 Percent**, **Graduate** has frequency of **86**

1.11 Reliability Test Using Cronbach Alpha

companies (employees in IT sector, Service sector, Automobile Industries, Government Organizations, Other Businesses) in the said age group. Time taken to collect the samples is about a month.

1.8 Statement of the Problem

Characteristics of Gen Z are studied and analyzed in connection to the facet model of advertising effectiveness and their various dimension having impact on Gen Z. Gen Z, the happening generational cohort plays a key role in sustenance of marketing communication of advertisers and branding strategists. Hence its effectiveness is studied in addition to integrating Gen Z characteristics to the term, 'Generational Advertising'.

1.9 Research Question

- Does Gen Z Characteristics determine 'Facet Model of Generational Advertising Effectiveness'?
- Does Facet Model of Generational Advertisement Effectiveness represent Brand Identity based on David Aaker Brand Identity Model.

at **21.5 Percent**, **Post Graduate** has frequency of **44** at **11 Percent** and **Diploma Holder** has frequency of **21** at **5.3 Percent**. Towards **Occupation**, Gen Z is employed in **IT Sector** show frequency of **50** at **12.5 Percent**, **Government** has frequency of **27** at **6.8 Percent**, **Industry** has frequency of **12** at **3 Percent**, **Service Sector** has frequency of **42** at **10.5%**, **Business** has frequency of **11** at **2.8 Percent** and **Unemployed and Student** has frequency of **258** at **64.5 Percent**.

Table 1.2 Reliability Test using Cronbach Alpha for Gen Z Characteristics

S.No	Gen Z Characteristics	Cronbach's Alpha	Sig.	N	Factors
1	Digital Native	.879	.000	400	2
2	Communaholic	.838	.000	400	3
3	Realistic	.828	.000	400	3
4	Singularity	.827	.000	400	3
5	Multiple Realities	.817	.000	400	3
6	Self-Expressive	.815	.000	400	3
7	Passionate	.801	.000	400	4
8	Dialoguer	.800	.000	400	4

Source: Primary Data Computed

1.13 Mean Ranks Of Gen Z Characteristics By Friedman Test

Objective: To critically evaluate Characteristics of Gen Z and analyse its effect on

advertisements based on **Facet Model** as target audience and advertised Brand Identity based on **David Aaker Model** as consumer segment.

Table 1.3 Friedman Test – Mean Ranks of Gen Z Characteristics

S. No	Gen Z Characteristics	Mean Rank (S)	Chi-Square Value	P Value
1	Passionate	7.08	2.784E3	.000
2	Dialoguer	6.70		
3	Communaholic	6.44		
4	Realistic	4.93		
5	Singularity	4.60		
6	Self-Expressive	2.84		
7	Digital Native	1.75		
8	Multiple Realities	1.66		

Source: Primary Data Computed

** Denotes significance at 1% level

H₀: There is 'No Significant Difference' in 'Mean Ranks' among Factors of Gen Z Characteristics. To test the stated hypothesis, **Friedman Test** was conducted on factors of **Gen Z Characteristics** and compare its 'Mean Ranks' to determine with statistical evidence that they are 'Not Significantly Different'.

Analysis of **Table 1.3** show, based on **Friedman Test** that there is 'Significant Difference' between 'Mean Ranks' of factors of **Gen Z Characteristics** at **Chi-Square Value 2.784E3** and **p value < .01**. Hence **Alternate Hypothesis** is 'Accepted' at **1% Significance**.

- (a) 'Passionate' with variables 'Visual Appeal, Trust, Fairness, Purpose' has 'Friedman Mean' of **7.08** serving as the **most important factor** of Gen Z Characteristics with **First Rank**.
- (b) 'Dialoguer' with 'Informative, Engage, Advocacy & Essence of Youth' as variables has 'Friedman Mean' of **6.70** with **Second Rank** as the **most important factor**.

Findings

Advertisers should focus on exhibiting brands as Purposeful, Trustworthy and Fair to 'Passionate' consumers. As advocacy is key, brands can advocate health and more related issues through advertisements for a 'Dialoguer'.

- (c) 'Communaholic' has 'Connect, Versatile & Personalize' with 'Friedman Mean' of **6.44** at **Third Rank**.
- (d) 'Realistic' has 'Entrepreneurial, Pragmatic,

Original' with 'Friedman Mean' of **4.93** at **Fourth Rank**.

- (e) 'Singularity' has 'Embrace Change, Express with Freedom, Undefined Identity' with 'Friedman Mean' of **4.60** at **Fifth Rank**.
- (f) 'Self-Expressive' has 'Social Cause, Set You Apart, Truth as Ideal' with 'Friedman Mean' of **2.84** at **Sixth Rank**.

Findings

Chance to express their ideas with freedom (**Singularity**), to connect with their identity as Gen Z (**Communaholic**), to support social cause and being truthful about its benefits, uses, quality / value etc., (**Self- Expressive**) is valued by Gen Z. Gen Z being a '**Singular**' Gen Z willing to embrace change in products and a key characteristic indicate they express their freedom for an identity in society. Providing truthful information with youthful spirit, engaging their entrepreneurial spirits, personalizing brand attributes and giving original, truthful facts (**Realistic**) matter to Gen Z.

- (g) 'Digital Native' has 'Symbolic Meaning and Know the Score' with 'Friedman Mean' of **1.75** with **Seventh Rank**.
- (h) 'Multiple Realities' with variables 'Transform, Variety Novelty Seeking & Meaningful Imagery' has 'Friedman Mean' of **1.66** at **Eight Rank** as important factor of Gen Z characteristic.

Findings

To utilize brand core aspects like Slogan, to give symbolic meaning to brand vision is suitable for '**Digital Native**' Gen Z and to apply meaning to

their existence and why brands exist in order to transform 'Multiple Realities' Gen Z, as audience. A market base in the present and in future can be realized by Gen Z through their Characteristics.

1.14 Model Fitness Of Gen Z Characteristics

1.14a Confirmatory Factor Analysis Of Gen Z

Table 1.4 Model Fitness by Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Gen Z Characteristics

Factor Indices For Model Fitness By Confirmatory Factor Analysis	Com	Dia	Dn	Mr	Pass	Real	Se	Sing
Chi-Square Value / DF	1.4	.6	.7	.73	.9	.43	1.02	.9
P Value	.10	.10	.52	.6	.7	.10	.42	.60
Goodness of Fit (GFI)	.984	.992	.999	.997	.988	.996	.992	.990
Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI)	.963	.984	.990	.989	.976	.990	.982	.981
Normal Fit Index (NFI)	.962	.976	.997	.992	.966	.991	.977	.960
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	.989	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Root Mean Square Residual (RMR)	.024	.02	.006	.006	.02	.010	.02	.021
Root Mean Square Approximation (RMSEA)	.031	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.007	.000

Source: Primary Data Computed

Analysis of Table 1.4 show that Confirmatory Factor Indices like Goodness of Fit (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI), Normal Fit Index (NFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI) of Gen Z Characteristics, 'Communaholic, Dialoguer, Digital Native, Multiple Realities, Passionate, Realistic, Self-Expressive and Singularity' are above 0.9; Root Mean Square Residual (RMR) and Root Mean Square Approximation (RMSEA) show less than 0.8 as a thumb rule. Hence 'Gen Z Characteristics' show 'Good Model Fit'.

Towards either Chi-Square < 0.5 or p Value

2 Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness

2.1 Reliability Test Using Cronbach Alpha For Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness

Table 2.1 Reliability Test (Cronbach Alpha) for Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness

S. No	Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness	Cronbach Alpha	N	Items
1	Perceive	.893	400	6
2	Connect	.837	400	4
3	Feel	.832	400	3
4	Understand	.807	400	4
5	Believe	.773	400	6

Source: Primary Data Computed

Table 2.1 shows 'Reliability' for 'Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness' with 'Perceive' at .893, 'Connect' at .837, 'Feel' at .832, 'Understand' at .807 and 'Believe' at .773. Primary Data collected show 'High Reliability' with Cronbach Alpha. It refers that as an instrument has attained high internal consistency and reliability.

Findings

Test result show 'High Reliability' is achieved at more than .8 for 'Perceive, Understand, Connect and Feel' and more than .7 for 'Believe' of Facet Model. Advertisement effectiveness measures

Table 2.2 Friedman Test – Mean Ranks of Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness

Characteristics By Spss - Amos

Objective: To critically evaluate Characteristics of Gen Z and analyse its effect on advertisements based on Facet Model as target audience and advertised Brand Identity based on David Aaker Model as consumer segment.

> 0.5 'Communaholic, Dialoguer, Digital Native, Multiple Realities, Passionate, Realistic & Singularity' show p value > 0.5 and Self-Expressive (0.42) < 0.5. Since p value and other indicators show 'Reliable Fitness' we accept the 'CFA Model as Fit' to proceed for 'Convergent Validity' and 'Discriminant Validity' analysis.

Findings

It is indicated that Gen Z is a dynamic cohort and in India, as a demographic and generational group, they exhibit their characteristics in their own way for an independent market base.

show 'Perceive' (Exposure, Attention, Awareness, Interest, Relevance and Recognition) as a main factor of Facet Model with 'High Reliability'.

2.2 Mean Ranks Of Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness Using Friedman Test

Objective: To study effectiveness of advertisement as a medium by integrating Gen Z Characteristics in measuring advertisement effectiveness using 'Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness' and its influence on them to be called 'Generational Advertising' and identifying Brand Identity Elements (David Model).

Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness	Mean Ranks	Chi-Square Value	P Value
Perceive	4.58	1.302E3	.000**
Believe	3.91		
Understand	3.49		
Connect	1.76		
Feel	1.27		

Source: Primary Data Computed

** Denotes significant at 1% level

H₀: There is **No Significant Difference** in **Mean Ranks** among Factors of **Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness** and in measuring advertisement effectiveness.

To test the stated hypothesis, **Friedman Test** was conducted on factors of 'Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness' and compare its 'Mean Ranks' to determine with statistical evidence that they are 'Not Significantly Different' in measuring the effectiveness of advertisements.

Table 2.2 indicate p-value as .000**, **Alternate Hypothesis** is 'Accepted'. It is concluded that there is 'Significant Difference' among 'Mean Ranks' of 'Perceive, Believe, Understand, Connect and Feel' as factors of 'Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness' and in measuring advertisement effectiveness at **Chi Square Value** of **1.302E3** at **1% Significance**.

Based on **Friedman Mean Ranks** it is shown that,

(a) 'Perceive' with 'Exposure, Attention, Awareness, Interest, Relevance and Recognition' as variables show 'Mean Rank' of **4.58**, is the **most important factor** of 'Facet Model' to measure Advertising Effectiveness that impacts Gen Z perception with **Friedman First Rank**.

Findings

Perceive is the **most important factor** to effect Gen Z, irrespective of age, gender, educational qualification and occupation, brands can consider them as homogenous group while targeting them as audience.

(b) 'Believe' with 'Motivation, Influence, Argument, Attitude, Involvement and Conviction' as variables show 'Mean Rank' of **3.91** that associates / persuades Gen Z's intention as Users to identify brands with **Friedman Second Rank**.

Findings

Believe is the **second most important factor** of Facet Model in measuring Advertising Effectiveness. 'Believe' is the final factor in the facet model and having the 'Second Highest Mean', imply that Gen Z consider believe as a criteria is vital in establishing advertisement effectiveness. Advertisers can consider how it can make Gen Z believe in what the ad says and why a brand exists is important.

(c) 'Understand' with 'Cognitive Learning, Information Need, Differentiation and

Recall' as variables show 'Mean Rank' of **3.49** to establish the need for Advertisement Effectiveness with cognitive impact to identify advertised brand's identity as audience and recall with **Friedman Third Rank**.

Findings

Understand is the **third most important factor** of Facet Model in measuring Advertising Effectiveness. It implies that advertisement shall provide brand information to differentiate its identity elements for better learning and recall.

(d) 'Connect' with 'Symbolism, Personality, Transformation & Brand Link' as variables show 'Mean Rank' of **1.76** links brands' ability to connect with Gen Z as target audience with **Friedman Fourth Rank**.

Findings

Connect is the **fourth most important factor** of Facet Model in measuring Advertising Effectiveness. It indicates that 'Connecting' the brand identity aspects to the target audience symbolize their personality, to link and transform their attitude towards brands.

(e) 'Feel' with 'Like, Emotion, Resonance' as variables show 'Mean Rank' of **1.27** to inform us that emotions and feelings resonate with Gen Z as audience to showcase and consider Facet Model of Advertisement Effectiveness as important with **Friedman Fifth Rank**.

Findings

Feel is the **last and fifth most important factor** of Facet Model in measuring Advertising Effectiveness. It indicates that 'emotional' aspects are important. Gen Z finds emotions, likes and feelings towards brands comes last in their analysis of ad effectiveness. Endorsers can emote, resonate with the audience, feel for a national brand etc. It is vital that the advertisement show myriads of emotions.

2.3 Model Fitness Of Facet Model Advertising Effectiveness

2.3a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Cfa) Of Facet Model Advertising Effectiveness

Objective: To study effectiveness of advertisement as a medium by integrating **Gen Z Characteristics** in measuring advertisement effectiveness using 'Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness' and its influence on them to be called 'Generational Advertising' and identifying Brand Identity Elements (**David Model**).

Table 2.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) of Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness

Factor Indices For Model Fitness By Confirmatory Factor Analysis Of Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness	PER	FEEL	UND	CON	BEL	Suggested Value
Chi-Square Value / DF	1.50 / 104	.389	.87	0.9	1.15	<.03/.05 (Hair, 1998)
P Value	.001	.994	.782	0.7	.190	> 0.05 (Hair, 1998)
Goodness of Fit (GFI)	.957	.996	.979	.989	.974	> 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI)	.937	.990	.966	.976	.959	> 0.90 (Hair, 2006)
Normal Fit Index (NFI)	.928	.988	.932	.979	.904	> 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	.974	1.000	1.000	1.000	.986	> 0.90 (Daire et al., 2008)
Root Mean Square Residual (RMR)	.024	.012	.025	0.02	.030	< 0.08 (Hair, 2006)
Root Mean Square Approximation (RMSEA)	.035	.000	.000	0.000	.019	< 0.08 (Hair, 2006)
Cronbach Alpha	.888	.832	.807	.837	.836	> 0.7

Source: Primary Data Computed

Table 2.3 indicate Confirmatory Factor Indices by conducting ‘GFI, AGFI, NFI, CFI’ that show ‘Good Model Fit’ for ‘Perceive, Feel, Understand, Connect and Believe’ as above 0.9; RMR & RMSEA show less than 0.8 which is adequate. Towards either Chi-Square < 0.5 or p value > 0.5 ‘Feel, Understand, Connect and Believe’ show p

value > 0.5 and ‘Perceive’ (0.001) < 0.5. Since p value and other indicators show ‘Reliable Fitness’, we accept ‘Confirmatory Factor Analysis’ as Model Fit to proceed to conduct ‘Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity’ Analysis on Data Set.

3 David Aaker Brand Identity Model

3.1 Reliability Test Using Cronbach Alpha Of David Aaker Brand Identity Model

Table 3.1 Reliability Test by Cronbach Alpha for David Aaker Brand Identity Model

S. No	Factors Of David Aaker Brand Identity Model	Cronbach Alpha	No. of Variables	N
	Brand Core Elements (BCE)	.892	8	400
	Brand As Product (BAP)	.853	8	400
	Brand As Symbol (BAS)	.827	5	400
	Brand Customer Relation (BCR)	.816	2	400
	Credibility – Corporate Voice (CCV)	.799	6	400
	Value Proposition (Benefits) (VP-B)	.767	3	400
	Brand As Organization (BAO)	.758	2	400
	Brand Position (BP)	.740	1	400
	Brand As Person (BAPS)	.858	3	400
	Value Proposition (14 Brands)	.831	14	400
	Core Brand User Persona (14 Brands)	.853	14	400
	Product & Organizational Attributes (14 Brands)	.873	14	400

Source: Primary Data Computed

Table 3.1 shows Reliability (Cronbach Alpha Test using IBM-SPSS) for David Aaker Brand Identity Model for ‘Brand Core & Elements’ at .892; ‘Product & Organizational Attribute’ at .873; ‘Brand as Person’ at .858; ‘Brand as Product’ at .853; ‘Brand as Symbol’ at .827; ‘Brand Customer Relation’ at .876; ‘Credibility – Corporate Voice’ at .799; ‘Value Proposition’ at .767; ‘Brand as Organization’ at .758; ‘Brand Position’ at .740, ‘Core Brand User Persona’ at .853 and ‘Value Proposition – Brands’

at .831. David Aaker Brand Identity Model show ‘High Reliability’ with measures more than 0.7 and 0.8. It infers that as an instrument, the model has attained high internal consistency and reliability suitable for further analysis.

3.2 Mean Ranks Of David Aaker Brand Identity Model Using Friedman Test

Objective: To Critically Evaluate David Aaker Brand Identity Model and its effect on Gen Z as a Model by identifying Advertised Brands’ Identity through ‘Generational Advertising’.

Table 3.2 Friedman Test (Mean Ranks) of Factors of David Aaker Brand Identity Model

S. No	David Aaker Brand Identity Model	Mean Rank (S)	Chi-Square Value	P Value
1	Brand Core Elements (BCE)	11.66	4.003E3	.000**
2	Brand As Product (BAP)	11.08		
3	Brand As Symbol (BAS)	9.65		
4	Credibility – Corporate Voice (CCV)	7.12		
5	Value Proposition (Benefits) (VP-BE)	4.96		
6	Brand Customer Relation (BCR)	3.63		
7	Brand as Organization (BAO)	2.22		
8	Brand Position (BP)	2.20		
9	Brand as Person (BAPR)	2.13		
10	Value Proposition (VP- 14 Brands)	8.17		
11	Product & Organizational Attributes (14 Brands)	7.82		
12	Core Brand User Persona (14 Brands)	7.38		

Source: Primary Data Computed

** Denotes significant at 1% level

H₀: There is **No Significant Difference** in **Mean Ranks** among Factors of David Aaker Brand Identity Model in identifying advertised brand identity.

To test the stated hypothesis, **Friedman Test** was conducted on factors of ‘**David Aaker Brand Identity Model**’ and compare its ‘**Mean Ranks**’ to determine with statistical evidence that they are ‘**Not Significantly Different**’ in identifying brand identity elements using the model.

Table 3.2 indicate p-value is .000**, the **Alternate Hypothesis** is ‘**Accepted**’ at **Chi-Square Value** of 4.003E3 and **1% Significance**. Hence concluded that there is ‘**Significant Difference**’ between **Mean Ranks** of factors of David Aaker Brand Identity Model and in identifying brand identity elements at **1% Significance**.

- (a) ‘**Brand Core Elements**’ with variables ‘Brand Core, Brand Name, Brand Logo, Brand Slogan, Tagline, Brand Vision, Brand Mission and Brand Extended Core’ has **Mean** of **11.66** where ‘**BCE**’ is the **most important factor** to establish ‘**David Aaker Brand Identity Model**’ with **Friedman First Rank**.
- (b) ‘**Brand as Product**’ with variables ‘Product Scope, Product Attribute, Quality, Value, Use, User & Country of Origin’ has **Mean** of **11.08** where ‘**BAP**’ plays a **key role in establishing** the advertised brand’s identity with **Friedman Second Rank**.
- (c) ‘**Brand as Symbol**’ with variables ‘Brand Symbol, Visual Imagery, User Imagery, Metaphor and Brand Heritage’ has **Mean** of **9.65** establishes ‘**BAS**’ as **important brand identity element** with **Friedman Third Rank** at **1% Significance**.
- (d) ‘**Value Proposition – 14 Brands**’ has **Mean** of **8.17** establishes identity of advertised brands stating their benefits to Gen Z with **Friedman Fourth Rank**.
- (e) ‘**Product & Organizational Attributes**’ has **Mean** of **7.82** identifies attributes of products and organizations and pointing its importance in

establishing brand identity with **Friedman Fifth Rank**.

- (f) ‘**Brand as Person - Core Brand User Persona**’ has **Mean** of **7.38** showcasing the **impact of brand personality** on Gen Z as target segment **Friedman Sixth Rank**.
- (g) ‘**Credibility – Corporate Voice**’ with variables ‘Credibility, Compelling, Memorable, Motivating, Meaningful and Believable’ has **Mean** of **7.12** elaborates brand’s **Corporate Voice** with **Friedman Seventh Rank**.
- (h) ‘**Value Proposition (Benefits)**’ with variables ‘Functional Benefits, Emotional Benefits and Self- Expressive Benefits’ has **Mean** of **4.96** expresses benefits of brands **are important to establish brand identities** with **Friedman Eight Rank** at **1% Significance**.
- (i) ‘**Brand Customer Relation**’ with variables ‘Brand Endorser and Brand Customer Relation’ has **Mean** of **3.63** impacts Gen Z through endorsers and relating with audience to identity brands with **Friedman Ninth Rank**.
- (j) ‘**Brand as Organization**’ with variables ‘Organizational Attributes and Local vs Global’ has **Mean** of **2.22** state that organizations can be identified using their attributes, local or global origin with **Friedman Tenth Rank**.
- (k) ‘**Brand as Person**’ with variables ‘Personality, Customer Brand Relationship’ has **Mean** of **2.13** informing brand’s personality helps to relate with them as identity elements with **Friedman Eleventh Rank**.

Findings

As Gen Z perceive, connect, understand, feel and believe brand identity elements, ‘**Brand Core & Elements, Brand as Product, Brand as Symbol, Brand as Person - Core Brand User Persona, Credibility – Corporate Voice, Value Proposition (Benefits), Brand Customer Relation, Brand as Organization, Brand as Person**’, as important, marketers can include brand identity elements in the Friedman mean rank order separately or together to create an impact on the target audience.

4.1 Pearson Correlation Coefficient Analysis

Objective: To critically evaluate inter-relationship between **Gen Z Characteristics** and **Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness** to be called '**Generational Advertising**' and **David**

Aaker Brand Identity Model and their effect as models on Gen Z, advertisement effectiveness and Brand identity of advertised brands.

Table 4.1 Inter-Relationship between Gen Z Characteristics, Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness and David Aaker Brand Identity Model

Models	Gen Z Characteristics	Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness	David Aaker Brand Identity Model
Gen Z Characteristics	1		
Facet Model Of Advertising Effectiveness	.833'' .000	1	
David Aaker Brand Identity Model	.699'' .000	.725'' .000	1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

H₀: Gen Z Characteristics, Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness and David Aaker Brand Identity Model show '**No Significant Relationship and Do Not Co-relate**' between each other as determining models.

To test the stated hypothesis, **Pearson Multiple Correlation Coefficient Analysis** was conducted on **Gen Z Characteristics, Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness** and **David Aaker Brand Identity Model** to frame **inter-relationship** between the models and to determine with statistical evidence correlation between the models '**Do Not Correlate with No Significant Relationship**'.

Analysis of **Table 4.1** indicate inter-relationship between **Gen Z Characteristics and Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness**. It is explained by **Pearson Correlation Coefficient (.833)** at **< .01** to '**Correlate with Significant Relationship**', where **Alternate Hypothesis** is '**Accepted**' as determinant models at **1% Significance**.

Inter-relationship between **Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness** and **David Aaker Brand Identity Model** is explained by **Pearson Correlation Coefficient (.725)** at **< .01** to '**Correlate with Significant Relationship**', where **Alternate Hypothesis** is '**Accepted**' as determinant models at **1% Significance**.

Inter-relationship between **David Aaker Brand Identity Model** and **Gen Z Characteristics** is explained by **Pearson Correlation Coefficient (.699)** at **< .01** to '**Correlate with Significant Relationship**', where **Alternate Hypothesis** is '**Accepted**' as determinant models at **1% Significance**.

Findings

Correlation between '**Facet Model of Advertising Effectiveness**' and '**Gen Z Characteristics**' is high at **83%**. It establishes the fact that '**Gen Z Characteristics**' are well represented in advertisements and its effectiveness are enhanced. Hence it can be called '**Generational Advertising**'. Correlation between '**Facet Model of**

Advertising Effectiveness' and '**David Aaker Brand Identity Model**' is high at **73%**. Thus the advertisements effectively represent Brand Identity Elements. Correlation between '**Gen Z Characteristics**' and '**David Aaker Brand Identity Model**' is high at **70%**. Thus Gen Z are able to identify Brand Identity Elements through advertisements.

Conclusion

Advertisements enhance their effectiveness for Gen Z as audience inclusive of identified characteristics. Advertisers can note that Gen Z as participants '**Perceive, Feel, Understand, Believe and Connect**' those characteristics involving them as target group of the advertised brands. Each Characteristic is different and can be highlighted with significant margin as each of those characteristics establishes them as Gen Z.

For Gen Z as a demographic segment, age, gender, education and occupation are important in deciding on brands. They are gender neutral and as Mckinsey Report says, they are homogenous. As each Gen Z Characteristic do not duplicate each other, it is suggested that marketers and advertisers can utilize each Gen Z Characteristics as '**Unique**' construct in their advertisements to identify brands and their brand identifiable elements based on **David Aaker Brand Identity Model**.

Reference:

1. Francis, Tracy and Hoefel, Fernanda (2012). "True Gen Z and its implications for companies". <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/consumer-packaged-goods/our-insights/true-generation-z-and-its-implications-for-companies>.
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3. Aaker A. David (1996). "Building Strong Brands". *The Free Press – Simon & Schuster, Inc.* New York.